

ISic4423

Fragment with Greek letters

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

unknown

Material

stone (type unknown)

Object

block

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2016 visited museum

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

unknown (assumed to be from the local area of Tripi)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Tripi, Museo Archeologico Santi Furnari di Tripi, inventory ME23440

Physical Description

A fragmentary block of coarse stone, damaged to left and right (and perhaps above and below also)

Dimensions

Height approx 18 cm

Width approx 33 cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

Three large, crudely cut Greek letters are preserved, filling the face

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Deeply cut letters of large size and somewhat irregular

Letter heights:

Line 1: approx 110 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. [---]ΔΔΤ[---]

Apparatus

text from photograph

Translation

Commentary

The inscription appears to be unpublished and requires further study/autopsy.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

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Photo M. Metcalfe